

README – Raw data upload for the article

“Boosting Conductance in Single-Molecule Junctions of Antiaromatic Dibenzopentalene”

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Raw data for the various analytical methods and calculations is compressed into one .zip file each for every method. The name of the file contains name of the compound (the structures of which can be found in the main article text). Further information regarding the data collection can be found in the supporting information of the main paper.

- Nuclear magnetic resonance (MNR)
 - Raw-data for each compound, either as folder or .dx-file (readable with BRUKER TopSpin or MESTRELAB MestReNova)
- Mass spectrometry
- Cyclic voltammetry
 - .txt files for the shown measurement and for the reference vs. Fc/Fc⁺
- Absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy
 - .txt files (for fluorescence spectra the excitation wavelength is given in the file name)
- Density functional theory (DFT) calculations
 - .xyz coordinate files of the optimized structure used as input for the NICS-calculations
 - .log files for the NICS(1)_{iso} calculations using Gaussian 16
 - xx-alldiff.armlog output file of the AROMA-script. The NICS(1.7) π_{zz} is the DEL-ZZ-Column.
- Single-molecule conductance measurements
 - The total data set, including all recorded plateau (Gz) traces and current-voltage (I-V) curves used in the manuscript, is contained in the zip files of ASCII data. These are simple text files, and can be read with many programs, such as Origin. The traces are fully transformed, meaning the distance, conductance, current and voltage scales are precise.

- The first and second columns of the .dat (ASCII) files prefixed with "Gz" correspond to the x and y axes. For the conductance (G) versus distance (z) traces, $x = z$ (in units of nm) and $y = G$ (in units of G_0).
- The first and second columns of the .dat (ASCII) files prefixed with "IV" correspond to the x and y axes. $x =$ voltage (in V) and $y =$ current (in A).